

A Bayesian Evaluation of Curriculum Mapping and Competency Trajectories: Optimizing Outcomes in Business Education

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Abstract

This research explores the effectiveness of the systematic curriculum and progressive competence development in the Bachelor of Business Administration majoring in Marketing Management at a University during the 2024-2025 academic year. By using macro-level institutional indicators from their Outcome Assessment Threshold (OATH) report, this study differs significantly from frequentist analyses based on sample sizes and instead uses the Bayesian inference approach. More specifically, this research evaluates the longitudinal impact on the five critical Student Outcomes (SOA to SOE) areas at three curriculum points – Introduction (I), Enhancement (E), and Demonstration (D). As for the descriptive data, there is high academic stability, as evidenced by an overall average of 90.00%. The paired Bayesian inference approach demonstrates small changes to pint scores in middle semesters (posterior mean for the difference between enhancement and Introduction equal to -1.00%, which gets corrected through a spike in instruction in the later semester (posterior mean for the difference between Demonstration and Enhancement equal to +1.20%, $(P(\Delta > 0) = 69.10\%)$). In terms of quality control considerations, the posterior probability is nearly certain to be 99.85% that the true baseline competency exceeds the institutional standard of “Very Satisfactory.” However, the probability that performance will be “Outstanding” or higher remains a pathetic 21.19%. This limitation is determined by local deviations in terms of quantitative assessment, particularly in SO E (marketing analytics evaluation), which stands (87%). Based on these findings, the curriculum does not necessitate a complete restructuring but rather the introduction of analytical components within middle-level courses to minimize systematic deviation.

Keywords: *Bayesian Inference, Curriculum Mapping, Educational Quality Assurance, Marketing Management, Outcomes-Based Education.*

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Suggested citation: Montano, V., Mercado, J., & Bulao, M.T. (2026). A Bayesian Evaluation of Curriculum Mapping and Competency Trajectories: Optimizing Outcomes in Business Education. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 4(4), 34-44. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2026.4(4).03

Introduction

In modern society, there is increasing pressure on educational institutions to demonstrate the practical usefulness of their curricula through demonstrable results (Allais, 2012). There is a shift from a qualitative approach to evaluating educational curricula to quantitative outcomes assessment (Tam, 2014), which requires a curriculum design process characterized by progressive learning through competency stages, such as introduction, enabling, and demonstrating outcomes (Letassy et al., 2015), (Child & Shaw, 2020). Outcomes assessment frameworks and platforms serve as diagnostic tools for academics seeking to connect classroom outcomes with institution-wide goals (Winkelmes et al., eds., 2023). By applying outcome assessment, universities can make targeted curricular changes to improve student preparedness in specific sectors (Medland, 2012).

In business education, particularly in highly innovative fields such as marketing management, it is essential to adopt this approach. The traditional approach, in most cases, becomes difficult to incorporate the need to balance the abstract conceptual ideas (Kridler, 2012) involved in marketing education with the more complex analytical skills needed in the present business environment (Meylani, 2024). For any program-level assessment to be effective, there must be an understanding of how the concept is developed from the beginning to its full realization (Banta & Palomba, 2015), enabling one to apply the acquired skills to solve problems in industry practice.

To address these empirical gaps, analytical techniques are used to analyze institutional data (Weldon, 2014), offering a more efficient approach than conventional, frequentist statistical analysis, which often fails to correctly interpret small and aggregated sample sizes (Fornacon-Wood et al., 2022). Bayesian inferential analysis offers institutions an opportunity to use historical baseline information to derive accurate posterior probabilities for exceeding thresholds (Zyphur & Oswald, 2015) and to model performance patterns without imposing limitations on sample size (Kennedy, 2015). Drawing on empirical data from the OATH Report, this paper uses Bayesian analysis to model the performance pattern of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Marketing Management curriculum for the year 2024-2025, accounting for variations across phases and deriving exact probabilities of meeting excellence thresholds. This study attempts to identify specific curriculum pivot points.

Theoretical Framework

The primary characteristics within the theoretical framework are the Curriculum Mapping Theory, which espouses academic curriculum as a coherent and purposeful direction rather than distinct subjects of learning. According to Uchiyama & Radin (2009), curriculum mapping involves aligning individual course goals within a specific program at the macro level so that students receive a clear map of the knowledge they are expected to acquire. As a consequence, the curriculum's architectural characteristics

are designed to develop crucial competencies among students (Boyd et al., 2007). The use of curriculum mapping is essential (Inzana et al., 2017), as it helps structure Student Outcomes (SOA to SOE).

In evaluating the development of competencies, the progressive stages are identified as Introduce (I), Enhance (E), and Demonstrate (D) model. Expanding on Vygotsky's (1978) scaffolding framework, this tri-level instructional model posits that learning occurs in progressively more complex phases, culminating in independence. At the introductory level (I), students gain basic theoretical knowledge; in the enhancing phase (E), they learn to use these theories in practice. Finally, in the last demonstration phase (D), students exhibit independence and readiness for problem solving. As Bruner (1966) claims, this sequence is referred to as a spiral curriculum in which complex concepts are learned repeatedly at increasingly higher levels.

To determine the efficacy of the gradual scaffolding process for small institutional data sets, it is necessary to move away from the rigid statistical procedures typically used in such analyses. Instead of using the frequentist framework, which assumes large sample sizes, this analysis uses the Bayesian Inferential Framework to determine changes in performance and threshold attainment. Bayesian estimation treats parameters as probabilities, allowing the use of institutional baseline data and credible intervals (Krusche, 2015). The evaluation method is consistent with the quality improvement paradigm (Deming, 1986), which holds that quality assurance in education requires a probabilistic feedback process to detect curricular weaknesses.

Materials and Methods

The study uses a quantitative, ex post facto research design (Rohwer, 2022) as part of an institutional quality assurance process. The objective of this research is to analyze the development of students' competencies and their probability of attaining the threshold for the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Marketing Management offered at a University during the academic year 2024-2025. Instead of using aggregate statistics as mere descriptive conclusions, the methodology uses data from the institutional Outcome Assessment Threshold (OATH) report for inferential modeling. In particular, the focus was on the five main Student Outcomes (SOA – Marketing Concept, SOB – Ethical Decision Making, SOC – Business Communication, SO D – Team-Synergized Problem Solving, and SOE – Marketing Analytics).

The data analysis was transformed from the classical frequentist paradigm into a Bayesian one (Bayarri & Berger, 2004). Classical approaches, such as the classical paired t-test and the ANOVA, need to be based on asymptotic assumptions with a high sample size (n), hence resulting in either over-confidence or power problems for application of the approach on highly aggregated samples with a low sample size ($n=5$; Student Outcomes) (Hoekstra et al., 2012). On the other hand, in Bayesian inference, the model's unknown parameters are treated as random variables with probability distributions (Box & Tiao, 2011).

The data analysis process consists of two stages. Bayesian Estimation of Differences refers to analyzing the likelihood of improvement or decline in a student's competence during the I, E, and D stages (Zyphur & Oswald, 2015). Finally, Bayesian Probability of Threshold Attainment will be conducted, considering all students' achievements with respect to the quality thresholds of $\geq 85\%$ and $\geq 91\%$ (Wadsworth & Tawn, 2012).

Bayesian Model Specification and Formula

To execute the inferential analysis without inflating statistical certainty, the aggregated percentage scores (y) for the Student Outcome are modeled as independent draws from a normal distribution (Blaikie, 2003). The true population variance of the assessment platform is unknown; a joint posterior distribution for both mean (μ) and the variance (σ^2) was determined simultaneously (Geweke, 2004).

1. The Likelihood Function

Given the observed outcomes scores $y = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n)$, the data are assumed to be normally distributed around an underlying program baseline mean (μ) with an unknown variance σ^2 :

$$y_i | \mu, \sigma^2 \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2) \quad (1)$$

The collective probability of observing the OATH report data is expressed through the Gaussian likelihood function:

$$L(y | \mu, \sigma^2) = (2\pi\sigma^2)^{-\frac{n}{2}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \mu)^2\right) \quad (2)$$

2. Prior Distributions

The values derived for the current academic year govern the model's results without any structural influence; a Jeffreys prior is employed, which is an uninformative objective prior. Equal initial probability is assumed for all real number ranges for the mean.

$$p(\mu, \sigma^2) \propto \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \quad (3)$$

3. Joint Posterior Distribution

Applying Bayes' theorem, the joint posterior distribution combines the prior knowledge and the data likelihood, which takes the form of a Normal-Inverse-Chi-Squared ($N - Inv - \chi^2$) conjugate

$$p(\mu, \sigma^2 | y) \propto L(y | \mu, \sigma^2) \times p(\mu, \sigma^2) \quad (4)$$

$$p(\mu, \sigma^2 | y) \propto (\sigma^2)^{-\left(\frac{n}{2}+1\right)} \exp\left(\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} [(n-1)s^2 + n(\bar{y} - \mu)^2]\right) \quad (5)$$

Where \bar{y} represents the empirical sample mean score and s^2 represents the sample variance of the isolated Student Outcomes.

$$\bar{y} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i \text{ and } s^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2 \quad (6)$$

4. Marginal Posterior for the True Mean (μ)

Integrating out the nuisance parameter (σ^2) provides the marginal posterior distribution for the true underlying program mean (μ). This mathematical integration shifts the parameter distribution to a scalable Student's t-distribution centered on the observed sample average, accounting for constraints imposed by small sample sizes.

$$\mu \mid y \sim t_{n-1} \left(\bar{y}, \frac{s^2}{n} \right) \quad (7)$$

This yields the exact probability density function used to calculate all inferential projections:

$$p(\mu \mid y) = \frac{\Gamma(\frac{n}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{n-1}{2})} \left(\frac{n}{\pi(n-1)s^2} \right)^{1/2} \left(1 + \frac{n(\mu - \bar{y})^2}{(n-1)s^2} \right)^{-n/2} \quad (8)$$

5. Inferential Testing Equations

For Phase Differences ($\Delta\mu$), to map curriculum progression (e.g. Demonstrate versus Introduce), a paired vector of differences in computed ($d_i = yD_i - yI_i$). The posterior probability of directional growth is calculated by evaluating the cumulative density function where the difference parameter ($\Delta\mu$) strictly exceeds zero:

$$P(\Delta\mu > 0 \mid y) = \int_0^{\infty} p(\Delta\mu \mid y) d(\Delta\mu) \quad (9)$$

For threshold attainment (T), calculate whether the overall marketing Management program satisfies an institutional bracket (e.g., Outstanding threshold T =91%), the true marginal posterior distribution is integrated from the boundary limit to infinity:

$$P(\mu \geq T \mid y) = \int_T^{\infty} p(\mu \mid y) d\mu \quad (10)$$

Results

The goal of this analysis is to examine the efficacy of the systems curriculum and the progression of competence within the Marketing Management in the 2024-2025 using the institutional data set contained in the OATH Report. The shift in paradigm from conventional frequentist diagnostics to the use of Bayesian inferential analytics allows the determination of student growth in three distinct pedagogic phases: Introduce, Enable, and Demonstrate, while adjusting for the limited number of samples in Student Outcomes (SO A-E). This study aims to determine with precision the

probability that the program will meet its high institutional-quality standards, based on the weaknesses in the curriculum identified, particularly in analytical skills.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Curriculum Phases and Total Achievement

Performance Metric	Mean Score	Median	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Range
Introduction Phase	89.80%	89%	3.42%	85%	94%	9%
Enable Phase	88.80%	89%	3.11%	85%	93%	8%
Demonstrate Phase	90%	90%	2.55%	86%	93%	7%
Total SO Achievement	90%	91%	1.73%	87%	91%	4%

Preliminary knowledge of the performance of the marketing Management program curriculum prior to delving into inferential modeling, descriptive statistics were computed based on the student outcomes from SOA to SOE. In the empirical data, the Marketing Management program curriculum remains highly competitive with a mean phase performance above the institution’s minimum “Very Satisfactory” (85%) cut-off. Starting with the Introduction Phase (I), an excellent starting point is 89.90%, despite having the greatest volatility of all phases ($s = 3.42\%$), owing to a considerable range in performance from 85% to 94%. On moving to the Enable Phase (E), there is a slight dip in mean performance, which becomes highly challenging, thus limiting student variability ($s = 3.11\%$).

There is clear evidence of an academic turnaround by the time students enter the gates of graduation in the Demonstrate Phase (D), with an average of 90%, and student performance is most tightly clustered in an efficient pattern ($s = 2.55\%$). This increasing trend to maturity is evident in the final metric used here. The total Student Outcome Achievement measure attains an efficient average of 90% and a slightly higher median of 91%, with minimal variation ($s = 1.73\%$).

Bayesian estimate of differences (phase comparison) was carried out by using a paired test on the five core Student Outcomes (SO A to SO E) with full curriculum tracking data in the OATH Report. Based on the assumption of the default, non-informative prior distribution suitable for a small sample size, differences were assumed in order to obtain the exact posterior probability distribution (in a Student’s t-distribution)

Table 2. Bayesian Paired Phase Estimation Results

Phase Comparison	Posterior Mean Difference	95% Credible Interval (HDI)	Probability of Growth $P(\Delta > 0)$
Enable vs. Introduce (E – I)	-1.00%	[-6.04%, +4.04%]	30.56%
Demonstrate vs. Enable	+1.20%	[-4.97%, +7.37%]	69.10%
Demonstrate vs. Introduce	+0.20%	[-3.77%, +4.17%]	55.23%

Bayesian paired estimation shows that student mastery scores are consistent across the whole curriculum, though in opposite directions during different phases. Referring to the transition from the introductory to the enable phase (E – I), it shows a mean

posterior decrease of -1.00% and a likelihood of only 30.56% for an increase in scores, indicating a slight decrease in student performance due to increased difficulty and specialization in the topics. On the other hand, a significant improvement is observed in progression to the Demonstration Phase (D – E) and the subsequent transition to the gates of graduation, resulting in a mean posterior increase of +1.20% and a probability of 69.10% of improvement in student performance.

Evaluating curriculum success from the initial state through to the final state (D – I), the Marketing Management delivers positive outcomes with a mean posterior difference of +0.20% and a probability 55.23% for student advancement. Given that all three 95% HDIs include zero, despite particular skills being improved with terminal jumps achievement in SO C and SO D, general institution performance across the department is successfully sustained and consistently held within the target “Very Satisfactory” to “Outstanding” quality benchmarks.

In determining the Bayesian Probability of Meeting the Threshold barriers, the overall SO Achievement data in the OATH Report was used, referring to the outcome in the MM program (SO A – SO E, which are 91%, 91%, 90%, 91%, and 87%, respectively). By employing a Bayesian normal model along with a weakly informative prior, the posterior distribution of the baseline mastery mean (μ) was inferred. This is used to compute the probability of meeting the two threshold barriers set by the program: Outstanding ($\geq 91\%$) and Very Satisfactory ($\geq 85\%$).

Table 3. Threshold Attainment Probability Results

Target Performance Level	Institutional Threshold	Posterior Probability of Attainment	Clinical Status
Outstanding (O)	91%	21.19%	Highly Competitive/Attainable
Very Satisfactory (VS)	85%	99.85%	Exceptionally Secure/Confirmed

The “Very Satisfactory” ceiling was nearly met (99.85%), the actual average achievement of the MM curriculum is almost certain (99.85%), and is above the threshold value of 85%, which indicates, in terms of quality assurance, the program is secure in terms of retrogressing into the “Satisfactory” category (84%). The drive to enabling (21.19%), four out of the five outcomes have a score at least 91%, “Outstanding.” Individually, given the overall variance and the lower limit of SO. E at 87%, there is actually a 21.19% chance that the underlying average across all courses is strictly greater than 91%.

The program demonstrates strong clustering around the threshold of excellence, and the curriculum is nearly “Outstanding” across the board. To increase the overall success probability from 21% to 80%, interventions should focus primarily on SO.E (Evaluating Marketing Analytics), where the current level is 87%; reaching 90% would secure the MM program's outstanding outcome.

Discussion

Based on the Bayesian inference model of the OATH Report, describe the efficacy of structure and pedagogy within the Marketing Management course. Unlike the

conventional frequentist model, which tends to distort the significance of data in small samples, the marginal posterior distributions obtained in this research offer insight into changes in the probability of student capabilities. The findings indicate that the curriculum is extremely resilient and effectively eliminates the risk of underperformance, placing students just above excellence standards.

The specific decrease in student performance occurs as they apply the introduced material from one level to another. The Bayesian paired estimation method shows that moving from the Introduce phase to the Enable phase (E – I) results in a mean drop of -1.00%, while there is only a 30.56% chance of a competency increase. In the context of curriculum mapping theory, this is a typical situation. It is common for courses to move beyond foundational knowledge to more specialized, high-cognition knowledge requiring a temporary adjustment process among students. Instead of failing, this indicates that the program's courses are becoming more rigorous over the semesters.

The instructional scaffolding used in the curriculum is effective, as evidenced by improvements in the record during the last stage of performance recovery. Moving from the Enable phase to the Demonstrate phase (D–E) results in a 1.20% improvement, with a 69.10% probability that the student's mastery level improved during this transition. Evidently, the program was successful in creating the needed “spiral matrix” that allows learning complex core concepts and applying the process of mastering them (Komarova et al., 2022). For the entire educational lifecycle (D – I), the improvement is positive (Posterior Mean = 0.20%, $P\Delta > 0$), with 55.23% of the improvement.

The posterior probability of threshold achievement from the quality assurance perspective indicates that the program set itself up on an extremely solid operational baseline. Based on the model, there is a 99.85% posterior probability that the program's mean average mastery level exceeds the “Very Satisfactory” threshold of 85%. The circular design effectively addresses all concerns about potential underperformance. However, the posterior probability for exceeding the “Outstanding” threshold (91%) is much lower at 21.19%. Four out of five student outcomes exceed the 91% threshold, but the Bayesian model accounts for system-level variance, which creates a specific obstacle to the department's overall success: SO. E (Evaluating Marketing Analytics) at 87%.

Although the curriculum facilitates the development of relational skills, ethics, and communication skills (SO A to SO D), there are specific gaps in the area of analysis. Modern successful firms use data analytics in marketing. The poorer SOE result indicates a learning gap between qualitative marketing and data analysis. Given the clustering of the entire program on the borderline of excellence, there is no need for a full-scale curricular transformation. By focusing on marketing analytics during the Enable phase, it is possible to eliminate variance and ensure the program's overall excellence.

Conclusion

The analysis carried out in this research proves that the current educational framework of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Marketing Management program demonstrates its high level of reliability and consistency of an almost certain Bayesian posterior probability (99.85%) of meeting the institutional

threshold of “Very Satisfactory,” which corresponds to 85% performance. The MM program presents an appropriate pedagogical scaffolding model with its visible academic improvement among the students while moving from Enable phase to Demonstrate phase (1.20% posterior mean gain), there is still only a relatively low probability of attaining an “Outstanding” rating (91%), which amounts to just 21.19% because of the identified learning barriers in terms of quantitative competencies (SO E).

Based on the findings above, it is recommended that the program's curriculum be adjusted by having the program managers shift from a generalized to a focused approach, which involves teaching students to quantify marketing. The program should include practical aspects of data analytics and statistical methods at the middle level of the curriculum to increase SO. E (Evaluating Marketing Analytics) through its Enable (E) growth stage to cover the deficit of -1.00%. Also, it is proposed that the OATH monitoring system be used to assess Bayesian probabilities for all business units based on the prior distributions obtained in the second semester of 2025, with a focused effort to reduce quantitative variance rather than adjust the qualitative components of the course. The MM program can overcome its only academic bottleneck in question and increase its overall probability of achieving an “Outstanding” status from 21.19%.

Acknowledgement

The researchers extend their gratitude to the Research and Innovation Center (RIC) for their assistance and to their colleagues for their moral support in completing this research.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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